

EOSC-IF

Computing Services Interoperability Guideline

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EOSC-IF / Compute Services Interoperability **Guideline**

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This version is to be reviewed by EOSC Interoperability Area Chairs

Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Abstract

This guideline proposes an extension of the EOSC profile v4.00 to describe and discover computing resources in the EOSC resource catalogue. This is a flexible metadata schema targeting services providing access to generic computing resources covering as much as possible the complete compute continuum: cloud, HTC and HPC and potentially the edge, including access to hardware accelerators (e.g. GPUs) in all these systems whenever available. The guideline describes the proposed extensions to the profile and shows examples of how it can be used with existing computing resources. The proposed schema does not attempt to create yet another standard for the usage of computing resources that will be unlikely to succeed. Instead, it aims at defining a common way for describing services that deliver computing resources so users can easily discover EOSC providers that can support their computational needs.

Version History

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V0.1	30/10/2021	Enol Fernández (EGI.eu) and Compute Continuum WG members https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/Compute+Continuum+Working+Group	First draft

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Table of Contents

1	5	
2	5	
3	5	
4	5	
5	8	
6	8	
7	8	
8	8	
	8.1	9
		8.2
		128.3.1
		13
	8.3.2	ComputingResourcePolicy
		13
9	16	Appendix A - Examples
		15
		Computing Resources Examples
		15
		Single VM flavour
		15
		Single VM flavour with GPU
		15
		CPU partition on a batch system: e.g LUMI standard node partition
		16
		Service and Provider examples
		18
		EGI Notebooks
		18
		EGI Cloud Compute General purpose option
		19

Table of Tables

Table 1.	ComputingService	9
Table 2.	Discovery Interface Types URIs	10
Table 3.	ComputingProvider	10
Table 4.	Computing Interface Types URIs	11
Table 5.	ComputingResource	11
Table 6.	AcceleratorResource	13
Table 7.	ComputingResourcePolicy	13

Table of Figures

Figure 1.	High Level Architecture of Computing Services	6
Figure 2.	VM Management Service Architecture	6
Figure 3.	Container Management Service Architecture	7
Figure 4.	Job Management Service Architecture	8
Figure 5.	Object model of the Compute Resources	9

Glossary

EOSC Future project Glossary is incorporated by reference: <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/x/JQCK>

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTC	High-Throughput Computing
PaaS	Platform as a Service
SaaS	Software as a Service
VM	Virtual Machine

1 Intended Audience

The intended audience for this EOSC Interoperability Guideline is the developers and technical experts from both community and commercial organisations that provide computing services to EOSC users, particularly those that would like their services to be discoverable via the EOSC Portal.

2 Description and main features

This guideline proposes an extension of the EOSC profile v4.00¹ to describe compute resources in the EOSC resource catalogue. This is a flexible metadata schema that allows for describing services providing access to generic computing resources covering as much as possible the complete compute continuum: cloud, HTC and HPC and potentially the edge, including access to hardware accelerators (e.g. GPUs) in all these systems whenever available.

3 Response to Community Need

Access to computing resources is a common requirement for all scientific disciplines. Computing needs can greatly vary from one community to another (or even within the same community depending on the specific problem at hand): from the more flexible IaaS approach where users have complete control of the hardware and software running to higher level abstractions (PaaS/SaaS) where users only deal with tasks (or jobs) that the computing platform will run in the most appropriate resources. Typically, the demand for computing resources is not constant and thus can benefit from a dynamic supply as a service approach following a cloud delivery model.

While there are multiple projects and initiatives delivering computing resources as a service in EOSC, there is no agreed technically interoperable specification that can be used for accessing these resources. Previous standardisation efforts in this area (e.g. OGF OCCI² and DMTF CIM³ for IaaS cloud providers, OGF BES⁴ for jobs) failed to gain the needed traction to make an impact, and this specification will not attempt to create yet another standard that will be unlikely to succeed. Instead, it aims at defining a common way for describing services that deliver computing resources so users can easily discover EOSC providers that can support their computational needs.

This specification mitigates the lack of standards in the compute service area and provides the basis for inter-operation by enabling the discovery and potentially automated usage of compute services by the user communities. Thanks to this metadata schema, user communities and single users with computing needs for a specific scientific aim can be triaged and dispatched to the most appropriate kind of compute platform according to their requirements.

4 High-level Architecture

This guide covers services delivering general purpose computing platforms where users interact with an API for the management of their workloads – which can be in the form of jobs, containers or VMs – on a set of computing resources, usually with associated local storage resources and networking to enable communication between the user workload components within the service and 3rd party external services. Figure 1 shows the general architecture that these services follow. An Orchestration Service can facilitate the access to several related Computing Services by providing a common interface to different types of Computing Services or by providing scheduling features to automatically allocate workloads into the most appropriate providers according to the user preferences. The Orchestration Service is not covered by this interoperability guideline but can use compliant services to automate the discovery, configuration and management of the user workloads, i.e. the Orchestration Service is a consumer of the specification provided in this guideline.

¹ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile>

² <https://ogf.org/documents/GFD.221.pdf>

³ https://www.dmtf.org/sites/default/files/standards/documents/DSPo263_2.0.0.pdf

⁴ <https://ogf.org/documents/GFD.108.pdf>

Figure 1. High Level Architecture of Computing Services

There are three main types of services that match the high level architecture: (i) VM Management services; (ii) Container orchestration services; and (iii) HTC/HPC Job Submission.

Figure 2 shows the high-level architecture for a VM Management service. A VM Management Service provides users with an API to manage Virtual Machines that are instantiated from VM images and can be associated with permanent block storage (volumes). The Virtual Machines can potentially execute any kind of workload, including new services or platforms that are accessed by platform users, which may be different from the VM Management users that manage the IaaS resources (often limited to expert users within a given community). OpenStack⁵ and OpenNebula⁶ are Open-Source products that deliver this kind of functionality. An IaaS Orchestration service may be used to facilitate the deployment and management of resources on one or multiple VM Management Service providers. Those services that offer the capability to manage Virtual Machines through graphical dashboards but do not provide API access cannot be considered interoperable as they cannot easily interchange information with or execute actions from other existing systems without human intervention.

Figure 2. VM Management Service Architecture

⁵ <https://www.openstack.org/>

⁶ <https://opennebula.org/>

The Architecture of Container Management Services is shown in Figure 3. Container Management Services provide users with an API to manage applications that are composed of containers. The container orchestrator manages a set of bare metal or IaaS Cloud resources where the containers are scheduled. The system also manages the containers lifecycle, associated storage for containers, provides networking among the application containers and exposes those as services to external applications, and scales up and down the deployments as needed. Other features related to container orchestration may be also provided. The main software product in this category is Kubernetes⁷.

Figure 3. Container Management Service Architecture

Figure 4 depicts the high-level architecture of the Job Management Services. In this case, users can submit their jobs by interacting with a Gateway node that delivers a well-defined API (e.g. ARC⁸ or HTCondor-CE⁹) or via a Login node that is usually accessed with ssh. This node will in turn interact with the local batch system (e.g. SLURM¹⁰) to submit the actual user jobs that are executed on a set of worker nodes with associated local storage. Depending on the hardware capabilities of the cluster and the type of jobs executed, e.g. loosely coupled tasks that can run in an independent manner or tightly coupled tasks that require low latency and high bandwidth interconnect, the system can support High-Throughput Computing (HTC) or High Performance Computing (HPC) models. As with the VM Management Service, an additional MetaScheduler or Orchestrator service can facilitate the interaction with multiple Job Management Service providers, taking decisions on behalf of the user on which individual provider to use for each job.

⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁸ <https://www.nordugrid.org/arc/ce/>

⁹ <https://htcondor.com/htcondor-ce/>

¹⁰ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

Figure 4. Job Management Service Architecture

5 Licensing Information

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6 Related Standards

Not Applicable

7 Integration Options

There is one integration option for this guideline: once implemented as an extension of the EOSC Resource Profile, providers can describe their resources using this specification. 3rd party tools will then be able to consume and automate the interaction with compute services based on the available information.

The specification is designed to allow for an incremental approach to publish information from a given provider, from the minimum mandatory information that will allow users and third party services to interact with the computing service with a clear understanding of the offered API; to a fully-detailed description of the available computing environment and their usage constraints that would allow the automated discovery and selection of providers and potentially the automated usage in those interoperable services (e.g. orchestrators).

8 Interoperability Guidelines

This guideline proposes an extension of the EOSC profile v4.00¹¹ to describe compute resources in the EOSC resource catalogue. This is a flexible metadata schema that allows for describing services providing access to generic computing resources covering as much as possible the complete compute continuum: cloud, HTC and HPC and potentially the edge, including access to hardware accelerators (e.g. GPUs) in all these systems whenever available.

¹¹ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile>

Figure 5. Object model of the Compute Resources

Figure 5 shows the object model for Compute resources. Services on EOSC can be of the ComputingService type which is supported by a set of ComputingProviders (this association supports federated services composed by multiple providers) which in turn will offer ComputingResources. Computing Resources may have associated accelerator resources and policies. The following sections describe each of these classes in detail.

8.1 ComputingService

The ComputingService is the main entry class for the specification. It extends the existing EOSC Service. It models a single entry in the EOSC Marketplace and is composed of a set of Providers that deliver the Computing Resources. This schema allows for the description of federated services where a single service is composed by multiple independent providers in coordination.

Services can also provide a discovery interface that allows users to query for additional information that may not be available in this specification. The Discovery Interfaces field points to external discovery interfaces that can be queried to get information about the computing services available. There is no mandated interface type, and every provider may have its own.

Table 1. ComputingService

ComputingService					
Code	Attribute Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required
CS.00	Id	Unique id of the service	String	1	Mandatory
CS.01	Name	Human readable name of the ComputingService	String	1	Optional
CS.02	Providers	List of ComputingProviders	ComputingProvider	Multiple	Mandatory

		included in this ComputingService			
CS.03	Discovery Interfaces	Discovery interface for the service. List of accessible APIs that can provide detailed information about the computing services defined. InterfaceTypes must be globally unique URI describing the interface provided for the discovery	List of pairs (URI, URL)	Multiple	Optional

Table 2 provides a non-exhaustive list of unique identifiers that can be used to describe the interface types.

Table 2. Discovery Interface Types URIs

URI	Description
http://forge.ogf.org/sf/projects/glue-wg/v2.0	OGF Glue Schema 2.0 - https://www.ogf.org/documents/GFD.147.pdf
http://forge.ogf.org/sf/projects/glue-wg/v2.1	OGF Glue Schema 2.1 - https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BpeTBQfCn8xRo4Ff38esRhBwzoUHE4bVxb2rEAzl-U/edit
https://is.appdb.egi.eu/rest	EGI AppDB Information System REST API - https://is.appdb.egi.eu/rest/
https://www.ivoa.net/documents/IVOA-EP-note	IVOA Execution Planner - https://github.com/ivoa/ExecutionPlannerNote

More types can be added as they are proposed.

8.2 ComputingProvider

A ComputeProvider is an EOSC provider that delivers computing functionality via a well-defined interface. It offers Computing Resources that are described with the ComputingResource type below. This specification extends the v4.00 EOSC Provider Profile¹², where some of its information such as an identifier (EPP.BAI.o) and Name (EPP.BAI.1) are already defined.

Table 3. ComputingProvider

ComputingProvider Information					
Code	Attribute Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required
EPP.CP.01	Type	URI that identifies the API/interface implemented by the Computing Provider	URI (see examples below)	1	Mandatory

¹² <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/A.+v4.00+EOSC+Provider+Profile>

EPP.CP.02	Computing Endpoint	URL for the endpoint that delivers the computing service following the interface described in EPP.CP.01	URL	1	Optional
EPP.CP.03	Computing Capabilities	Capabilities of this Computing Provider. Key-value labels that can help findability of the computing provider (e.g. HPC: True).	Key-Value	Multiple	Optional
EPP.CP.04	External Connectivity	Type of network connection towards external resources. In this version of the spec, it is provided as a free text field. This field may be refined in later revisions.	String(100)	1	Optional
EPP.CP.04	Related Resources	List of other Resources that are commonly used with this Resource (e.g. storage services)	ResourceID	Multiple	Optional
EPP.CP.05	Computing Resources	List of computing resources from this provider	Computing Resources	Multiple	Optional

Table 4 provides a non-exhaustive list of unique identifiers that can be used to describe the Computing endpoint interface types. This may be turned into a controlled vocabulary on later versions of this guideline.

Table 4. Computing Interface Types URIs

URI	Description
https://openstack.org/compute/v2.1	(Cloud IaaS) OpenStack Compute (Nova) API v2.1,
https://ec2.amazonaws.com/	AWS EC2 API
<a href="https://kubernetes.io/api/<vx.y.z>">https://kubernetes.io/api/<vx.y.z>	Kubernetes API (vx.y.z)
https://github.com/ga4gh/task-execution-schemas	GA4GH TES
https://www.nordugrid.org/arc/arc6	NorduGrid ARC-CE 6
https://htcondor.org/htcondor	HTCondor
https://slurm.schedmd.com/	SLURM
https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyterhub	JupyterHub
https://github.com/jupyterhub/binderhub	BinderHub
https://zeppelin.apache.org/	Apache Zeppelin

8.3 Computing Resource

A `ComputingResource` provides information about the resources for users to execute their applications. It can model an instance (flavour) type in an IaaS cloud infrastructure, a partition in a batch system, or a set of nodes in a Kubernetes cluster. It extends the v4.00 EOSC Resource Profile¹³, so it assumes some information such as an identifier (ERP.BAI.0) and Name (ERP.BAI.1) are already defined.

A `ComputingResource` object models resources as a set of similar nodes with some hardware resources associated to them (CPU, RAM, Accelerators, disk) which can be combined to form larger allocations (e.g. a parallel job can run across multiple of these nodes in an HPC computer). The model allows for describing heterogeneous sets of these nodes in a single object (e.g. for a batch system partition with different kind of nodes), but it is not meant to cover all the aspects of these as the modelling would be too complex and hard to maintain reasonably updated without introducing too much overhead from the resource providers. The information provided should be enough to get a first good understanding on whether a given provider can support the workload requirements of a user.

The discovery endpoints of the `ComputingService` can provide additional information that cannot be covered by this specification.

Table 5. *ComputingResource*

ComputingResource Information					
Code	Attribute Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required
ERP.CR.01	Min Node Core Count	Minimum Number of CPU cores available on a single node of this computing environment. For a VM, this refers to the number of CPUs available for the VM (not the hypervisor)	Float ¹⁴	1	Optional
ERP.CR.02	Max Node Core Count	Maximum Number of CPU cores available on a single node of this computing environment. For a VM, this refers to the number of CPUs available for the VM (not the hypervisor)	Float ¹²	1	Optional
ERP.CR.03	Min Node RAM	Minimum RAM available on a single node of this computing environment (in GB). For a VM, this refers to the RAM available for the VM (not the hypervisor)	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.04	Max Node RAM	Maximum RAM available on a single node of this computing environment (in	Float	1	Optional

¹³ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile>

¹⁴ Using Float to cover cases where cores are not fully assigned to a given user, in most of the cases this will be an Integer.

		GB). For a VM, this refers to the RAM available for the VM (not the hypervisor)			
ERP.CR.05	Bare Metal	True if there is no virtualisation	Boolean	1	Optional
ERP.CR.06	Architecture	CPU architecture (as returned by <code>uname -m</code>). Those providers supporting multiple architectures should have different "ComputeResource" objects defined	String	1	Optional
ERP.CR.07	cpuinfo	CPU information as obtained by <code>lscpu --json</code> in linux, so it can be parsed.	String (json)	1	Optional
ERP.CR.08	Node Accelerators	Available accelerator resources (e.g. GPU, FPGA) available at the nodes	Accelerator Resource Type	Multiple	Optional
ERP.CR.09	Network Type	A free-text description of the networking capabilities of the computing resources. May be refined in later versions of this specification	String	1	Optional
ERP.CR.10	Inbound Connectivity	True/False depending on whether the node can receive network connections from outside the provider or not	Boolean	1	Optional
ERP.CR.11	Outbound Connectivity	True/False depending on whether the node can start network connections to outside the provider or not	Boolean	1	Optional
ERP.CR.12	Policy	Usage policies associated to the resource	Computing Resource Policy	1	Optional

8.3.1 AcceleratorResource

The AcceleratorResource describes a set of accelerators available in the nodes of a computing environment described by the ComputingResource type.

Table 6. AcceleratorResource

AcceleratorResource Information					
Code	Attribute Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required
ERP.CR.AR.01	Type	Type of accelerator provided	Enumerated (FPGA, GPU, other)	1	Mandatory
ERP.CR.AR.02	Description	A free-text description of the accelerator, e.g. "NVIDIA A100"	String(100)	1	Mandatory
ERP.CP.AR.03	Vendor	Vendor identification as returned by lspci -nn, e.g. "NVIDIA Corporation [10de]"	String	1	Optional
ERP.CP.AR.04	Device	Device information as returned by lspci -nn, e.g. "GV100GL [Tesla V100 SXM2 32GB] [1db5]"	String	1	Optional
ERP.CP.AR.05	Capabilities	Key-value labels that can help to further describe the accelerator (e.g. CUDA: 10.x).	Key-Value	Multiple	Optional
ERP.CP.AR.06	minCount	Minimum number of this type of accelerators available	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CP.AR.07	maxCount	Maximum number of this type of accelerators available	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CP.AR.08	memory	Memory in GB for each of the accelerators	Float	1	Optional

8.3.2 ComputingResourcePolicy

A ComputingResourcePolicy provides information about the policies (i.e. limits) on usage of the available resources. It's commonly used in HPC/HTC type of systems where there are partitions with limits associated with them.

Table 7. ComputingResourcePolicy

ComputeResourcePolicy Information					
Code	Attribute Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required

ERP.CR.CRP.01	Min NodeCount	Minimum Number of nodes that are allocated to users within this computing environment.	Integer	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.02	Max NodeCount	Maximum number of Nodes that are allocated to users within this computing environment	Integer	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.03	Min WallTime	Minimum wall time allocated to users (in seconds), if not specified no minimum is enforced	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.04	Max WallTime	Maximum wall time allocated to users (in seconds), if not specified no maximum is enforced	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.05	Max CPUTime	Maximum CPU time (in seconds) allocated to users, if not specified there is no limit	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.06	Max AcceleratorTime	Maximum Accelerator (GPU) time in seconds that can be used within this package, if not specified there is no limit	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.07	Min CPUcount	Minimum number of CPU cores that can be used within this resource type	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.08	Max CPUcount	Maximum number of CPU cores that can be used within this resource type	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.09	Min RAM	Minimum amount of RAM (in GB) for the computing environment	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.10	Max RAM	Maximum amount of RAM (in GB) for the computing environment	Float	1	Optional
ERP.CR.CRP.11	Full-node	Whether the allocation is using full nodes or not	Boolean	1	Optional

Examples

Examples are given in Appendix A

9 Examples of solutions implementing this specification

There are no implementations of the specification as this requires the extension of the EOSC Resource Profile. EGI Cloud Compute service is ready to publish information following this specification leveraging the AppDB Information System that contains a superset of the metadata included in the specification.

Appendix A - Examples

Computing Resources Examples

A `ComputeResource` provides information about the resources for users to execute their applications. It can model an instance (flavour) type in an IaaS cloud infrastructure, a partition in a batch system, or a set of nodes in a Kubernetes cluster. In this section we show several examples on how it can be used by providers.

Single VM flavour

IaaS Cloud providers deliver access to computing resources in the form of Virtual Machines, these are normally offered in pre-defined sizes, types or flavours (naming largely depends on the provider). Providers can model each offered size with a `ComputeResourceType` object. For example, a *tiny* OpenStack flavour with an x86 1 CPU, 2 GB of RAM could be modelled as follows:

ComputeResourceType			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.01	Min Node Core Count	1	Flavour with 1 CPU
ERP.CR.02	Max Node Core Count	1	
ERP.CR.03	Min Node RAM	2	2 GB of RAM
ERP.CR.04	Max Node RAM	2	
ERP.CR.05	Bare Metal	False	VM running on an hypervisor
ERP.CR.06	Architecture	x86	This is x86 hardware
ERP.CR.07	cpuinfo	{... full json object from lspci -json ..}	Full output not included to avoid overloading the document
ERP.CR.08	Node Accelerators	null	No accelerators
ERP.CR.09	Network Type	GB Ethernet	Free Text description of the network
ERP.CR.10	Inbound Connectivity	True	In/Oubound network connections are possible
ERP.CR.11	Outbound Connectivity	True	
ERP.CR.12	Policy	null	No specific limits for VMs

Single VM flavour with GPU

This example expands the previous one by adding accelerator information. An OpenStack flavour with an x86 16 CPU, 64 GB of RAM and 1 NVIDIA V100 GPU could be modelled as follows:

ComputeResourceType			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.01	Min Node Core Count	16	Flavour with 16 CPU
ERP.CR.02	Max Node Core Count	16	

ERP.CR.03	Min Node RAM	64	64 GB of RAM
ERP.CR.04	Max Node RAM	64	
ERP.CR.05	Bare Metal	False	VM running on an hypervisor
ERP.CR.06	Architecture	x86	This is x86 hardware
ERP.CR.07	cpuinfo	{... full json object from lspci -json ..}	Full output not included to avoid overloading the document
ERP.CR.08	Node Accelerators	See below	Accelerator described in table below
ERP.CR.09	Network Type	GB Ethernet	Free Text description of the network
ERP.CR.10	Inbound Connectivity	True	In/Oubound network connections are possible
ERP.CR.11	Outbound Connectivity	True	
ERP.CR.12	Policy	null	No specific limits for VMs

Accelerators of the VM:

AcceleratorResource			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.AR.01	Type	GPU	It is a GPU
ERP.CR.AR.02	Description	NVIDIA V100	Human readable description
ERP.CP.AR.03	Vendor	NVIDIA Corporation [1ode]	As returned by lspci
ERP.CP.AR.04	Device	GV100GL [Tesla V100 SXM2 32GB] [1db5]	As returned by lspci
ERP.CP.AR.05	Capabilities	["CUDA version": "0.6"]	May be normalised for upcoming versions of the specification
ERP.CP.AR.06	minCount	1	1 V100 available in the flavour
ERP.CP.AR.07	maxCount	1	
ERP.CP.AR.08	memory	32	Each V100 has 32 GB of memory

CPU partition on a batch system: e.g LUMI standard node partition

This example models one of the available partitions in LUMI as described in <https://docs.lumi-supercomputer.eu/runjobs/scheduled-jobs/partitions/#slurm-partitions-allocatable-by-node> – allows access to up to 512 LUMI-C nodes for a maximum of 2 days.

ComputeResourceType

Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.01	Min Node Core Count	128	LUMI-C nodes have 128 CPU cores
ERP.CR.02	Max Node Core Count	128	
ERP.CR.03	Min Node RAM	256	Nodes with 256, 512 and 1024 GB of RAM
ERP.CR.04	Max Node RAM	1024	
ERP.CR.05	Bare Metal	True	HPC
ERP.CR.06	Architecture	x86	This is x86 hardware
ERP.CR.07	cpuinfo	{... full json object from lspci -json ..}	Full output not included to avoid overloading the document
ERP.CR.08	Node Accelerators	null	No accelerator for these VMs
ERP.CR.09	Network Type	1x 200 Gb/s	Free text description of the network
ERP.CR.10	Inbound Connectivity	False	In/Outbound network connections are NOT possible
ERP.CR.11	Outbound Connectivity	False	
ERP.CR.12	Policy	See below	Policy described in table below

ComputeResourcePolicyType			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.CRP.01	Min NodeCount	1	Maximum 512 nodes can be used per job
ERP.CR.CRP.02	Max NodeCount	512	
ERP.CR.CRP.03	Min WallTime	null	2 days limit
ERP.CR.CRP.04	Max WallTime	2880	
ERP.CR.CRP.05	Max CPUTime	null	No CPU time limit
ERP.CR.CRP.06	Max AcceleratorTime	null	No accelerator available
ERP.CR.CRP.07	Min CPUcount	null	No explicit limit set (according the public documentation)
ERP.CR.CRP.08	Max CPUcount	null	
ERP.CR.CRP.09	Min RAM	null	No explicit limit set (in the public documentation...)
ERP.CR.CRP.10	Max RAM	null	

ERP.CR.CRP.11	Full Node	True	Full nodes used here
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Service and Provider examples

EGI Notebooks

EGI Notebooks offers access to Jupyter notebooks via EGI Check-for identity. It offers “Notebooks for researchers” as a computing environment with no time limits on the usage, but only 1 session can be started at any given time.

Computing Service			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
CS.00	Id	https://www.egi.eu/service/notebooks/	Unique ID of the service
CS.01	Name	EGI Notebooks	Name
CS.02	Providers	See below	
CS.03	Discovery Interfaces	null	There are no additional discovery endpoints for this service

ComputingProvider			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
EPP.CP.01	Type	https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyterhub	This is a JupyterHub service
EPP.CP.02	Computing Endpoint	https://notebooks.egi.eu	URL for accessing the service
EPP.CP.03	Computing Capabilities	null	No extra capabilities defined
EPP.CP.04	External Connectivity	null	Information not revealed
EPP.CP.04	Related Resources	[“ https://www.egi.eu/service/replay/ ”]	EGI Replay is a BinderHub deployment
EPP.CP.05	Computing Resources	See below	ComputingResources are defined in its own object

ComputeResourceType			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.01	Min Node Core Count	0.5	

ERP.CR.02	Max Node Core Count	2	EGI Notebooks default session is initially assigned 0.5 cores and can use up to 2 cores
ERP.CR.03	Min Node RAM	0.5	Guaranteed 512MB of RAM, can reach up to 6GB
ERP.CR.04	Max Node RAM	6	
ERP.CR.05	Bare Metal	False	Running on VMs
ERP.CR.06	Architecture	x86	This is x86 hardware
ERP.CR.07	cpuinfo	null	This information is not provided
ERP.CR.08	Node Accelerators	null	No accelerator for Notebooks default session
ERP.CR.09	Network Type	null	Information not revealed for this service
ERP.CR.10	Inbound Connectivity	False	Cannot open listening ports
ERP.CR.11	Outbound Connectivity	True	
ERP.CR.12	Policy	See below	Policy described in table below

ComputeResourcePolicyType			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
ERP.CR.CRP.01	Min NodeCount	1	1 session per user
ERP.CR.CRP.02	Max NodeCount	1	
ERP.CR.CRP.03	Min WallTime	null	No time limit
ERP.CR.CRP.04	Max WallTime	null	
ERP.CR.CRP.05	Max CPUTime	null	No CPU time limit
ERP.CR.CRP.06	Max AcceleratorTime	null	No accelerator available
ERP.CR.CRP.07	Min CPUcount	null	Up to 2 CPUs
ERP.CR.CRP.08	Max CPUcount	2	
ERP.CR.CRP.09	Min RAM	null	Up to 6GB RAM
ERP.CR.CRP.10	Max RAM	6	
ERP.CR.CRP.11	Full Node	null	This information is not revealed

Additional ComputeResourceType can be associated with the Provider for other types of Notebook sessions, such as GPU enabled or with different limitations.

EGI Cloud Compute General purpose option

EGI Cloud Compute is a federated OpenStack service that delivers several VM flavours from different providers. In this example we show how to model a ComputeResource that delivers access to general purpose VMs that can be described with a single object, grouping common characteristics. This simplifies the presentation in the EOSC portal and allows federated providers to still deliver relevant information without overwhelming the users.

Computing Service			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
CS.00	Id	https://www.egi.eu/service/cloud-compute/	Unique ID of the service
CS.01	Name	EGI Cloud Compute	Name
CS.02	Providers	See below	
CS.03	Discovery Interfaces	["https://is.appdb.egi.eu/rest", "https://is.appdb.egi.eu/rest"]	AppDB offers additional information using AppDB API

ComputingProvider			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes
EPP.CP.01	Type	https://openstack.org/compute/v2.1	OpenStack interface
EPP.CP.02	Computing Endpoint	null	Multiple endpoints, there is no single URL that can be used here, so not describing it
EPP.CP.03	Computing Capabilities	null	No extra information available
EPP.CP.04	External Connectivity	null	As this object is covering multiple providers, not defined
EPP.CP.04	Related Resources	null	EGI Online Storage is usually used in conjunction with this.
EPP.CP.05	Computing Resources	See below	ComputingResources are defined in its own object

ComputeResourceType			
Code	Attribute Name	Value	Notes

ERP.CR.01	Min Node Core Count	1	Flavours from 1 to 8 CPUs
ERP.CR.02	Max Node Core Count	8	
ERP.CR.03	Min Node RAM	1	Flavours with 1 GB to 16 GB of RAM
ERP.CR.04	Max Node RAM	16	
ERP.CR.05	Bare Metal	False	VM running on a hypervisor
ERP.CR.06	Architecture	x86	This is x86 hardware
ERP.CR.07	cpuinfo	null	As this represents several VM types, not included
ERP.CR.08	Node Accelerators	null	No accelerator for these VMs
ERP.CR.09	Network Type	GB Ethernet	Free Text description of the network
ERP.CR.10	Inbound Connectivity	True	In/Outbound network connections are possible
ERP.CR.11	Outbound Connectivity	True	
ERP.CR.12	Policy	null	No specific limits for VMs